

Karnataka State College Librarian's Association(R), Bangalore

6th KSCLA

International Conference On

PARADIGMS OF DIGITAL LIBRARY, E-RESOURCES, OPEN ACCESS AND INFORMATION AND MEDIA LITERACY

ICPDL 2015

Conference Proceedings

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. Ashok Y. Asundi

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PREFACE

The advent of electronic and digital information sources has added a new dimension to the libraries in general and academic libraries in particular. The scholarly literature is the backbone of teaching, learning and research activity which are prime objectives of academic institutions; the colleges and universities. The library is adorned as the 'heart of university's academic activity' and the supporting role played by libraries is solely depended on the information resources they acquire, possess and organize for the ease of use by the library clientele. Since the beginning of new millennium the impact of ICT on libraries has been envisaged first by the automating the libraries, library networking for sharing information resources and then gradually moving towards emergent situation of born digital information resources and normally termed as e-resources.

The new paradigmatic management of libraries emerged with the advent of Digital Library concept, originated in the early 1990s and the birth of Internet and proliferation of Web environment provided enough impetus to the growth of born digital resources, especially the scholarly communication, in particular, electronic journals, electronic books, electronic reference books all important and essential reading and learning materials for the users - students, teachers and academicians. The growth of scholarly literature, the information aggregation and consolidation received a shot in arm with the supporting cost effective technology for capture, storage, management and delivery of electronic resources to the academic community. This trend gradually gave a way for the establishment of digital libraries and electronic resource sharing consortia. So the trend has thrown out a technology that was responsible for creation of born digital as well as retrospective creation of digital resources and this has made every nation to initiate digital library work. There is vast growth of electronic, internet and Web resources for restricted as well for free access.

The digital library representation of scholarly literature also brought with it some constraints of free sharing and access to the electronic resources. So a new concept was initiated at the dawn of new millennium - the Open Access to scholarly literature, so emerged the Open Access initiatives and it is progressing as a movement.

The next area of discussion that was associated with these developments is the user dilemma, the change from P-environment to E-environment. The print media was represented by physical and tangible objects and accessible through the library systems. But the electronic version changed the physical environment to virtual environment and that information was intangible and required special skills, knowledge and ability to search, access and document the retrievable information. There emerged a need for educating the user about the effective use of the new resources and which gave way for a new Education programme called Information Literacy - an enlightened extension of hither-to- before called the User Education.

So three to four paradigms have dimensioned on libraries attached to the Academic Libraries and a thorough discussion on these new these dimensions viz. Digital Libraries, Electronic Resources, Open Access and Information and Media Literacy was found to be impending as the academic librarians are challenged by the new electronic and digital environment which has been making a lasting impact. So the Karnataka State College Librarians Association (KSCLA) aptly thought of organizing an "International Conference on the Paradigms of Digital Library, Electronic Resources, Open Access and Information and Media Literacy" for two days on 9th and 10th October 2015. The Conference obviously scheduled on five basic themes;

- ❖ Digital Library
- ❖ Electronic Resources
- ❖ Open Access and;
- ❖ Information and Media Literacy
- ❖ LIS Curriculum and Best Practices

of concern to the Academic Libraries and in particularly to the College Libraries.

The Organisers enabled LIS professionals to contribute and to deliberate on the five issues by Librarians working in College Libraries to write papers and in this regard received nearly 106 papers particularly from them. The Organisers also sought Invited papers from few experts on the four broad themes to contribute and all the papers are included in this Conference volume in order to encourage particularly budding young authors.

We hope that this conference volume will become a useful addition to the world of literature in library and information Science.

Place:

Date

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Best Practices @ BLDE University (Medical) Central Library, Vijayapur

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ABSTRACT

There has been tremendous surge in educational Institutions coming up particularly after creation of All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE) in 1987. The surge is more in private sector which has opened flood gates in private sectors Institutions. Number of deemed Universities and Colleges come up recently. In the same way the development of ICT has also changed the users' expectation from the academic libraries in different ways. To meet the end users demands effectively, the academic libraries has to identify and adopt good practices and benchmarks. Thus, preparing guidelines in a standardized way based on the best practices employed by libraries is significant which will ultimately enhance the value based services of academic libraries. This paper discussed on the meaning and definition of best practices in accordance with National Academic Accreditation Council (NAAC) and some of the best practices followed by BLDE University (Medical) Central Library at Vijayapur, Karnataka in particular.

Key words: Best practices; library; library management; softwares; NAAC

1. Introduction

University form the important and integral part of Higher education and libraries in university are the primary source for learning process. The university library is a connecting link between teaching and learning as well as place which supplements its resources what is beyond scope of class room. University libraries play an important role in the educational history of Students, Researcher, as well as the faculty members. It serves the students, Research Scholars and faculty by providing specific information. But how far the university libraries are successful in implementing their goals into its reality is a big question.

There must be some agency to have a proper vigilance on the functioning of university libraries and also to suggest certain measures to rectify the emerging needs, and for this purpose NAAC was established for assessing the quality of education and maintenance of the institutions.

2. Meaning & Definition

Meaning: Best Practice may be innovative and be a philosophy, policy, strategy, program, process or practice that solves a problem or create new opportunities and positively impact on educational institutions. Institutional excellence is the aggregate of the best practices followed in different areas of institutional activities. In general, the use of technology and innovative ideas lead to evolve best practices in library and information environment.

Definition: ODLIS (Reitz, 2004) defined term 'best practices' as follows: "In the application of theory to real-life situations, procedures that, when properly, applied consistently yield superior results and are therefore used as reference points in evaluation of the effectiveness of alternative methods of accomplishing the same task. Best practices are identified by examining empirical evidence of success."¹

2.1 Objectives of best practices:

- To provide up-to-date knowledge to Students, Research Scholars and Faculty in their subject field.

- To help students for their educational development through internet.
- To ensure the use of on-line books, journals and other e-resources, etc.
- To extend library services / facilities to the Students, Researchers and Faculty of the neighboring institutions in the society.

3. BLDE University at Vijayapur:

BLDE University is one amongst the reputed Universities in Karnataka, providing education in various Medical Courses. Housed in a sprawling campus at Vijayapur (former Bijapur) in Karnataka, It was declared a University under sec 3 of the UGC Act 1956 and approved by Ministry of Human Resource development. It has been established under BLDE Association, a renowned educational Society, running more than 75 institutions in the state.

BLDE University was established as a Deemed University under sec 3 of the UGC Act 1956. The Constituent College of the University, Sri. B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Center, Vijayapur, was established in the year 1986 by BLDE Association Bijapur (Bijapur Liberal Development Education Association)

BLDE University has the necessary infrastructure and equipments for imparting Medical Education. It houses the college departments, central Library and residential quarters in various blocks spread across a huge campus. There are separate hostels for boys, girls, NRI students and PG students. The university Library has enviable collection of books, journals, E-books, E-journals, back volumes etc which are available for faculty and students for reference. Besides all these amenities, the University maintains state -of- the- art laboratories for providing teaching and research facilities.

3.1 BLDE University Central Library:

Central Library established in the year 1986. It serves as a resource center for health science information. Also serves as a gateway to the electronic and print biomedical information. Library's primary clientele are the University's Students, Faculty, Research Scholars, Staff and outside health science professionals. Apart from this, to provide ready references at work place, 21 departmental libraries were established.

Central Library developed a set of best practices under the following four major areas:

- ❖ Central Library working hours:
- ❖ Collection and Development.
- ❖ Service and Facilities for Users.
- ❖ Use of Technology.

3.1.1 Central Library Working Hours:

- **Library Opening Hours:** All the 365 days in a year
- **Transaction Hours:** 8:00 AM TO 10:00 PM in all the 365 days in an year
- **Reading facility:** Round the Clock (24X7) in All the 365 days in an year

Very few libraries in the world have this type of working hours and attract more number of users during holidays. All the sections in the library kept opens from morning 08:00AM to 10:00PM in all the days irrespective of Sundays, general holidays, local holidays etc in three shifts basis and serves in the interest of its users.

3.1.2 Collection and Development:

The Central Library has enviable collection of books and other information resources as follows:

Particulars	Total	Particulars	Total
Books	17371	HELINET E Database-Books	3835
Back Volumes of Journals	7378	HELINET E-Journals	295
National Journals	75	PROQUEST Health and Medical complete Database	
International Journals	76	PROQUEST Nursing and Allied Health source Database	
Dissertations	451	E - Books (Print + online)	90
News Papers	13	E - Journals (Print + online)	128
Magazines	13	Audio Cassettes	118
		Video Cassettes	52
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Picture-1 Central Library Circulation Counter

These four major areas are highly integrated, but libraries that excel in organizing material sources and in leading their human capital are known to give better performance.

Routine library activities like cataloguing, check ins - checkouts, renewal of books & journals and inventory of users (entry & exit), OPAC etc. are being handled through a good library management software called NewGenLib (Version NGL Core Engine 3.1.1) and it is an open source by nature and the source codes can be customized according to requirement of the particular library and we in our Central Library of BLDE University, Vijayapur are using all modules of the NGL to their best.

Picture-2 Circulation Module in NGL

Picture-3 Inventory of Users in NGL

Library is automated with NGL 3.1.1 library management open source software. The main aim of the collection development is to make available all types of important reading material, i.e. General books, reference books, text books, reports, patents, theses, Dissertations, serials, journals, non-book material resources etc to support learning, teaching and research pursuits of readers of the college by the active University Library Committee.

3.1.3 Services and Facility for Users:

All types of Library services are providing for users in BLDE University Central library. Few best practices in this area are as follows:

- Current Awareness Services (CAS)
- Literature Search through database and internet resources
- Document Delivery Service (DDS)
- Reprographic Service
- Referral Service
- News Paper clipping Service.
- E-mail alert Service
- SMS alert Service
- Electronic Resource Search through Internet.
- Repository of old question papers (Soft copy) available for students.
- Repository of research publication published by the faculty maintained through D Space

Facilities for Users:

- ❖ Wi-Fi Facility available in the Library.
- ❖ OPAC (Online Public Access Catalogue).

- ❖ Facility for Video Conference.
- ❖ Reading Rooms with air conditioned provided for students.
- ❖ Book Bank Facility available for SC/ ST Students.
- ❖ Purified Drinking water, separate Rest Rooms for ladies and gents in each floor.
- ❖ Mini Cafeteria in the Library
- ❖ Separate Ramp provided for physically challenged.
- ❖ Visitor Tracking facility (registering of Entry / Exit of Users in the computer system)
- ❖ Other facilities: CD Writer/ Printers, Scanning of documents available for users.

3.1.4 Use of Technology in the Library:

Central Library of BLDE University uses the state of the art technology for its library operations, services & facilities as follows:

The students and faculties are provided 50 computer systems with 50 mbps bandwidth Internet facility to full fill their educational needs like filling up e-scholarship forms, use HELINET & Proquest Consortia journals, e-books, check emails, get information from govt. websites, fill online job application forms and check results online, etc and faculty get information

Picture- 4 Digital Library

about the research made in their concerned subjects as well as to take help from internet sources in their teaching learning methods including reading materials.

Picture-5 HELINET webpage @ BLDEU Central Library